

Keywords:

#marine habitat mapping, #OpenScience, #mesophoticzone, #remotesensingdata, #ADAMPlatform #ResearchObjects, #FAIRprinciples, #EOSCinPractice

Mapping Mesophotic Habitats with EOSC Services and Tools

Enhancing Marine Habitat Mapping through Remote Sensing and Research Object Preservation

The project involved

The EU-funded RELIANCE project seeks to extend the capabilities of the EOSC with enhanced support for a range of research activities aligned with the EOSC Interoperability Framework. This will make it easier to find and use research data, including Copernicus data, simplify extraction of relevant information, and effectively managing the research lifecycle via research objects. The project also supports the principles of FAIR and open science.

"Marine habitat mapping aims at providing a holistic representation of ecologically relevant marine habitats, their associated biological communities, their areal extent, distribution patterns, status, and physical conditions."

Giorgio Castellan, Postdoctoral Researcher at CNR-ISMAR Institute of Marine Sciences, RELIANCE

The Research Community

The marine habitat mapping community brings together ecologists, biologists, and geologists to provide accurate and extensive maps of marine habitats, the community aims at detecting environmental changes in marine habitats using an ecological approach to support marine spatial planning, to help reduce the cost of monitoring programmes and provide environmental impact assessments.

The Challenge

Marine habitat mapping provides a holistic representation of ecologically-relevant marine habitats, their associated biological communities, areal extent, distribution patterns, status, and physical conditions. The mesophotic zone, part of the water column with dim light conditions, can host a diverse mosaic of benthic habitats, hotspots of biodiversity. However, the mesophotic domain depends on light conditions that vary considerably depending on geographical location. Satellite and remote sensing data can be used to map the extension and distribution of the mesophotic zone, providing information to support the conservation and management of the biodiversity the zone hosts. Integrating and processing satellite/remote sensing data, however, can be challenging in terms of data mining, data accessibility and computational resources. This was one of the main challenges of the project.

EOSC service or tool used

A Python script was used to model the mesophotic zone using EGI Jupyter Notebook (notebooks.egi.eu). Satellite data on Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) and diffuse attenuation coefficient for light at 490 nm were then obtained from the ADAM Platform (reliance.adamplatform.eu) and used to map the Mediterranean mesophotic zone. A Research Object was created in ROHub (reliance.rohub.org) containing the inputs and outputs of the model, and the Jupyter Notebook running the model. As this is fully public and accessible, the Research Object can not only be included in future research, but it is also findable on OpenAIRE Explore (explore.openaire.eu) and Zenodo (zenodo.org).

Useful tips & tricks

The ADAM Platform (reliance.adamplatform.eu) allows the extraction of global and local remote-sensing data from past and current times, as well as short-term forecast and long-term projections. By collecting data from different sources, such as Copernicus, NASA Ocean Color, etc., ADAM makes remote-sensing data from different repositories easily-findable and accessible, from the web platform and from Jupyter Notebook (ADAM API).

ROHub (reliance.rohub.org) is a holistic solution for the storage, lifecycle management, and preservation of scientific investigations via research objects. It makes these resources available to others, allows publishing and releasing them through a DOI, also through Zenodo, allowing to discover and reuse of existing scientific knowledge. The Research Objects can also be accessed from EOSC OpenAIRE Explore.

Benefits and impact

EOSC services provided a set of tools that ensured the research process followed FAIR principles. The Jupyter Notebook allowed the model to run in a collaborative and powerful environment and the process to be shared with other researchers. The interoperability with ADAM Platform ensured the exploration and access of a large volume of remote-sensing data, used as inputs for the model. Further, the encapsulation of the research process in a Research Object allows our research to be easily accessible to other researchers, boosting the impact of the research itself. The reproducibility of scientific approaches, sharing methods, and results are of primary relevance for the scientific community, allowing to capitalize on available information to increase the knowledge of our oceans.

Why do I need EOSC?

"Within the Habitat Mapping community, I used to run my models and work on local environments and share the results through direct contacts" states Giorgio Castellan, Postdoctoral Researcher at CNR. *"However, scientific research is moving fast towards a more collaborative approach,*

both in terms of methods and exploration and capitalization of existing data. The EOSC services simplified the collection of existing information on marine habitats and remote-sensing data, strongly reducing the amount of time dedicated to this task. Further, the EOSC tools made my research activities to be more reproducible and sharable with other experts. I found very useful the set of services developed and included in the EOSC portfolio related to remote-sensing."

Across disciplines

Marine habitat mapping is based on the integration of ecological, biological, and geological aspects to provide accurate and extensive maps of marine habitats. In the past, searching for information on different research themes required a huge amount of time, often relying upon personal contacts. The EOSC Portfolio helps overcome this barrier, allowing different disciplines and expertise to combine in a powerful and modern environment.

Useful material related to this story

» <https://www.reliance-project.eu/>

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